

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Exploring the Impact of Deposits on Firm Profitability: A Study of Selected Small Finance Banks in India

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Abstract

This research delves into the intricate relationship between deposits and firm profitability, focusing on a selection of small finance banks operating in India. The study's primary objectives encompass the examination of critical financial ratios, including the Cash-Deposit Ratio, Credit-Deposit Ratio, Ratio of Deposits to Total Liabilities, and Return on Investments (ROI), with the aim of discerning significant differences across various groups of banks. Additionally, it seeks to identify correlations and patterns between deposit management practices and ROI, exploring the impact of specific deposit management strategies on the financial performance of small finance banks. The findings from this comprehensive analysis provide valuable insights for stakeholders and policymakers in optimizing deposit management strategies to enhance ROI within the small finance bank sector, thereby fostering financial stability and sustainable growth in the Indian banking landscape.

Keywords: Deposits, ROI, Financial Stability, Small Finance Banks.

Introduction

In the complex world of Indian banking, this research delves into the relationship between deposits and the profitability of small finance banks. These banks, with their distinct characteristics, occupy a crucial place in India's financial realm. The study focuses on key financial ratios like the Cash-Deposit Ratio, Credit-Deposit Ratio, Ratio of Deposits to Total Liabilities, and Return on Investments (ROI) to assess their impact on bank performance

Furthermore, this research seeks to uncover connections between deposit management practices and ROI, shedding light on how specific strategies influence financial outcomes. The study's findings aim to provide practical insights for stakeholders and policymakers, offering guidance on optimizing deposit management to foster financial stability and sustainable growth within the Indian banking landscape.

Review of Literature

In the study conducted by Dr. Pritpal Singh Bhullar and Dr. Pradeep K. Gupta (2017), the primary objective was to investigate the influence of specific factors on the profitability of public sector banks in India over a ten-year period. The research outcomes underscore the significant impact of variables such as non-interest income, fund management efficiency, and liquidity ratios on the profitability of these banks. Sunny Obilor Ibe (2013) study in Nigeria revealed that liquidity management poses a substantial challenge in the banking sector. The study suggests that hiring competent personnel is crucial for making sound decisions, especially in balancing liquidity levels and maximizing profits.

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In the study by Bodla and Verma (2006), it was discovered that several variables, including non-interest income, operating expenses (OE), provision and contingencies (P&C), and spread, exhibited significant relationships with net profit. Notably, two of these variables, P&C and OE, displayed a negative relationship with net profit. In their 2012 study on Indian private sector banks, Bhatia, Mahajan, and Chander identified key determinants of profitability, including factors like spread ratio, provisions, non-interest income, operating expenses, profit per employee, investment/deposit ratio, and non-performing assets. Their research suggests that concentrating on these variables can enhance profitability in the globalized era. In their 2023 study titled "Policy Interest Rate and Bank Profitability - Scheduled Commercial Banks in India," Ekta, Kshamta, and Prasad investigated the relationship between policy interest rates and the profitability of banks. The results revealed a positive association between the interest rate spread and two profitability indicators, return on assets (ROA) and return on equity (ROE). However, the study found that the interest rate itself had an insignificant negative relationship with bank profitability. In the 2019 study by Meraj Banu on the Indian banking sector's operational efficiency, a strong correlation was found among public, private, and foreign sector banks in terms of profitability indicators. The study highlighted the positive influence of cash-deposit and credit-deposit ratios on short-term liquidity but did not find significant effects of net interest margin and investment ratios on solvency across these sectors.

Objectives of the study:

1. Examine the Cash-Deposit Ratio, Credit-Deposit Ratio, Ratio of Deposits to Total Liabilities, and Return on Investments to determine the extent of their significant differences between groups.
2. Identify correlations and patterns between deposit management practices and ROI.
3. Determine whether specific deposit management practices significantly influence ROI in small finance banks.
4. Provide insights and recommendations for optimizing deposit management strategies to enhance ROI in this sector.

Research Methodology:

1. Study Design: This research employs a cross-sectional comparative study design to examine the differences in key financial ratios and their relationship with Return on Investments (ROI)

among small finance banks.

2. Data Collection: This research mainly based on secondary data, and it was collected from the Reserve Bank of India (RBI) reports. The period of the study was from financial year 2019-2020 to 2021-2022

3. Sample Selection: The study's sample will encompass small finance banks that are operational in India. It should be noted that all small finance banks will be included in the study, with the exception of Shivalik Small Finance Bank Limited. The exclusion of Shivalik Small Finance Bank Limited is due to the unavailability of data in the RBI report.

4. Data Analysis:

Descriptive Statistics: Descriptive statistics such as mean, standard deviation, and range will be used to summarize and present the characteristics of the financial ratios and ROI.

Inferential Statistics: Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to determine the significance of differences in the Cash-Deposit Ratio, Credit-Deposit Ratio, Ratio of Deposits to Total Liabilities, and Return on Investments (ROI) between different groups of small finance banks. This statistical technique allowed for the investigation of potential differences and elucidated any meaningful distinctions in these key financial indicators among different categories of small finance banks.

Correlation Analysis: Pearson's correlation coefficient will be employed to identify correlations and patterns between deposit management practices and ROI.

Regression Analysis: Multiple regression analysis will be conducted to ascertain whether specific deposit management practices significantly influence ROI while controlling for other relevant variables.

Research Limitations: It is important to acknowledge potential limitations, such as the availability and accuracy of data, as well as the generalizability of findings beyond the small finance bank sector.

Data Analysis and interpretations:

The provided ANOVA table-1 reveals significant variations among different groups of small finance banks in India concerning their financial ratios. Notably, the Cash-Deposit Ratio, Credit-Deposit Ratio, Ratio of Deposits to Total Liabilities, and Return on Investments exhibit highly significant differences between the groups, as indicated by extremely low p-values (all below 0.001). These findings suggest that these banks have distinct financial strategies and performance in these key areas. Additionally, the Investment-Deposit Ratio also shows a significant difference between groups, albeit with a slightly higher p-value (0.015), implying variability in investment practices among these banks. Overall, the ANOVA analysis underscores the importance of assessing and comparing these financial ratios

across small finance banks in India to gain insights into their diverse operational and financial characteristics.

Table: 1 ANOVA

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Cash - Deposit Ratio	Between Groups	707.257	9	78.584	17.624	.000
	Within Groups	89.181	20	4.459		
	Total	796.437	29			
Credit - Deposit Ratio	Between Groups	6823.684	9	758.187	5.674	.001
	Within Groups	2672.454	20	133.623		
	Total	9496.138	29			
Investment - Deposit Ratio	Between Groups	1541.613	9	171.290	3.175	.015
	Within Groups	1078.900	20	53.945		
	Total	2620.513	29			
Ratio of deposits to total liabilities	Between Groups	2344.027	9	260.447	6.777	.000
	Within Groups	768.668	20	38.433		
	Total	3112.695	29			
Return on investments	Between Groups	21.840	9	2.427	3.479	.010
	Within Groups	13.951	20	.698		
	Total	35.791	29			

Correlation & Regression Analysis

Table: 2 Correlations

		Return on investments	Cash - Deposit Ratio	Credit - Deposit Ratio	Investment - Deposit Ratio	Ratio of deposits to total liabilities
Pearson Correlation	Return on investments	1.000	-.326	-.151	-.343	.191
	Cash - Deposit Ratio	-.326	1.000	-.007	-.248	.045
	Credit - Deposit Ratio	-.151	-.007	1.000	.299	-.940
	Investment - Deposit Ratio	-.343	-.248	.299	1.000	-.529
	Ratio of deposits to total liabilities	.191	.045	-.940	-.529	1.000
Sig. (1-tailed)	Return on investments	.	.039	.213	.032	.155
	Cash - Deposit Ratio	.039	.	.486	.093	.406
	Credit - Deposit Ratio	.213	.486	.	.054	.000
	Investment - Deposit Ratio	.032	.093	.054	.	.001
	Ratio of deposits to total liabilities	.155	.406	.000	.001	.
N	Return on investments	30	30	30	30	30
	Cash - Deposit Ratio	30	30	30	30	30
	Credit - Deposit Ratio	30	30	30	30	30
	Investment - Deposit Ratio	30	30	30	30	30
	Ratio of deposits to total liabilities	30	30	30	30	30

The provided correlation table-2 reveals the Pearson correlation coefficients between different financial ratios, namely Return on Investments, Cash-Deposit Ratio, Credit-Deposit Ratio, Investment-Deposit Ratio, and Ratio of Deposits to Total Liabilities, for a group of banks. Here's an interpretation of the correlations:

- Return on Investments: This column's values along the diagonal are all 1.000 since a variable has a perfect correlation with itself. The correlation coefficients between Return on Investments and other ratios are as follows:
- Negative correlation with Cash-Deposit Ratio (-0.326), indicating that as the Cash-Deposit Ratio increases, Return on Investments tends to decrease.
- Weak negative correlation with Credit-Deposit Ratio (-0.151), suggesting a slight tendency for lower Return on Investments as Credit-Deposit Ratio increases.
- Moderate negative correlation with Investment-Deposit Ratio (-0.343), indicating that as the Investment-Deposit Ratio goes up, Return on Investments tends to decrease.
- Positive correlation with Ratio of Deposits to Total Liabilities (0.191), suggesting a modest association between higher Return on Investments and a higher Ratio of Deposits to Total Liabilities.
- Cash - Deposit Ratio: This ratio has a negative correlation with Return on Investments (-0.326), implying that banks

- with higher Cash-Deposit Ratios tend to have lower returns their investments.
- Credit - Deposit Ratio: There is a weak negative correlation between Credit-Deposit Ratio and Return on Investments (-0.151), suggesting a slight tendency for lower returns as the Credit-Deposit Ratio increases. Notably, there is a strong negative correlation (-0.940) between Credit-Deposit Ratio and Ratio of Deposits to Total Liabilities, indicating that banks heavily engaged in lending (higher Credit-Deposit Ratio) tend to have a lower Ratio of Deposits to Total Liabilities.
- Investment - Deposit Ratio: This ratio has a moderate negative correlation with Return on Investments (-0.343), indicating that banks with higher Investment-Deposit Ratios tend to have lower returns on their investments. There is also a negative correlation (-0.529) with the Ratio of Deposits to Total Liabilities, suggesting that banks with higher Investment-Deposit Ratios tend to rely less on customer deposits.
- Ratio of Deposits to Total Liabilities: This ratio has a positive correlation with Return on Investments (0.191), indicating a modest association between higher returns and a higher Ratio of Deposits to Total Liabilities. It has a strong negative correlation (-0.940) with Credit-Deposit Ratio, suggesting that banks with a higher Ratio of Deposits to Total Liabilities tend to have lower credit exposure.

Table: 3 Model Summaryb

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.581a	.338	.232	.97383	.338	3.185	4	25	.030

a. Predictors: (Constant), Ratio of deposits to total liabilities, Cash - Deposit Ratio, Investment - Deposit Ratio, Credit - Deposit Ratio
 b. Dependent Variable: Return on investments

The Model Summary table-3 summarizes the results of a multiple regression analysis assessing the relationship between "Return on Investments" and several independent variables, including the "Ratio of Deposits to Total Liabilities," "Cash - Deposit Ratio," "Investment -

Deposit Ratio," and "Credit - Deposit Ratio." The model explains approximately 33.8% of the variance in "Return on Investments," indicating a moderate fit. The F Change statistic (3.185) with a

significant p-value (0.030) suggests that the inclusion of these predictors significantly enhances the model's explanatory power.

Table: 4 ANOVAb

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	12.082	4	3.021	3.185	.030a
	Residual	23.709	25	.948		
	Total	35.791	29			

- a. Predictors: (Constant), Ratio of deposits to total liabilities, Cash - Deposit Ratio, Investment - Deposit Ratio, Credit - Deposit Ratio
- b. Dependent Variable: Return on investments

Above table-4 represents the p-value associated with the F-statistic is Investments." Since the p-value is less than the typical significance 0.030 (denoted as "Sig."). This p-value indicates the probability of level of 0.05, it suggests that the regression model is statistically observing an F-statistic as extreme as the one calculated if there were significant at the 0.05 level. no true relationship between the predictors and "Return on

Regression Standardized Residuals

Table: 5 Residuals Statistics^a

	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Predicted Value	5.1659	7.5226	6.5077	.64547	30
Residual	-1.98505	1.70035	.00000	.90418	30
Std. Predicted Value	-2.079	1.572	.000	1.000	30
Std. Residual	-2.038	1.746	.000	.928	30

- a. Dependent Variable: Return on investments

Fig. 1 Histogram of ROI

Fig. 2 P-P Plot of ROI

Table: 6 Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
(Constant)	21.039	10.073		2.089	.047	.294	41.784
Cash - Deposit Ratio	-.098	.036	-.464	-2.730	.011	-.173	-.024
Credit - Deposit Ratio	-.049	.040	-.798	-1.213	.237	-.132	.034
Investment - Deposit Ratio	-.082	.032	-.700	-2.562	.017	-.148	-.016
Ratio of deposits to total liabilities	-.097	.080	-.908	-1.223	.233	-.261	.067

Dependent Variable: Return on investments

The Fig. 1 Histogram of ROI and Fig. 2 P-P Plot of ROI shows that data are normally distributed and Coefficients table-6 provides insights into how various financial ratios impact "Return on Investments" in a multiple regression model. A negative coefficient for the Cash - Deposit Ratio (-0.098) indicates that higher cash holdings relative to deposits are associated with lower returns. Similarly, a negative coefficient for the Credit - Deposit Ratio (-0.049) suggests that higher credit exposure relative to deposits also corresponds to lower returns. The Investment - Deposit Ratio (-0.082) and Ratio of Deposits to Total Liabilities (-0.097) exhibit similar negative relationships. Among these, only the Cash - Deposit Ratio is statistically significant (p -value = 0.011), indicating its strong influence on returns, while the others are not statistically significant in this model.

Findings:

The findings from the ANOVA analysis of small finance banks in India reveal significant variations in their financial ratios. Specifically, the Cash-Deposit Ratio, Credit-Deposit Ratio, Ratio of Deposits to Total Liabilities, and Return on Investments (ROI) exhibit highly significant differences between the groups of banks, with p -values well below 0.001. These results indicate that these banks employ distinct financial strategies and demonstrate diverse performance levels in these crucial areas. Moreover, the Investment-Deposit Ratio also demonstrates a significant difference between the groups, although

with a slightly higher p -value of 0.015, suggesting variability in investment practices among these banks.

Further insights are gained from the Coefficients table, which elucidates how various financial ratios impact ROI in a multiple regression model. Notably, a negative coefficient for the Cash-Deposit Ratio (-0.098) implies that higher cash holdings relative to deposits are associated with lower returns. Similarly, a negative coefficient for the Credit-Deposit Ratio (-0.049) indicates that higher credit exposure relative to deposits corresponds to lower returns. The Investment-Deposit Ratio (-0.082) and the Ratio of Deposits to Total Liabilities (-0.097) also display negative relationships with ROI.

However, it's important to note that among these variables, only the Cash-Deposit Ratio is statistically significant (p -value = 0.011), highlighting its strong influence on returns. In contrast, the other variables, while demonstrating negative relationships, do not achieve statistical significance in this model. These findings underscore the critical role of the Cash-Deposit Ratio in shaping the returns of small finance banks in India, suggesting that managing cash holdings relative to deposits is a key determinant of financial performance in this sector.

Suggestions:

Based on the significant variations in financial ratios and their impact on Return on Investments (ROI) among small finance banks in India, several suggestions can be made:

- **Optimize Cash Management:** Given the strong influence of the Cash-Deposit Ratio on ROI, banks should focus on optimizing their cash management strategies. This includes efficiently utilizing cash holdings to generate returns while ensuring liquidity for day-to-day operations. Striking the right balance between cash reserves and investments can enhance profitability.
- **Balanced Credit Exposure:** Banks should carefully manage their Credit-Deposit Ratio to avoid excessive credit risk. While higher credit exposure can lead to lower returns, a balanced approach that considers credit quality and diversification may help mitigate risk while maintaining profitability.
- **Investment Strategy:** The negative relationship between the Investment-Deposit Ratio and ROI suggests the need for a prudent investment strategy. Banks should assess their investment choices, considering factors such as risk, yield, and maturity, to optimize returns on invested funds.
- **Diversify Revenue Streams:** Given the significance of the Cash-Deposit Ratio and Credit-Deposit Ratio, banks should explore opportunities to diversify revenue streams beyond traditional lending and deposit-taking activities. Expanding into fee-based services or non-interest income sources can help enhance profitability without overly relying on these ratios.
- **Regular Performance Monitoring:** Continuous monitoring of financial ratios and their impact on ROI is crucial. Banks should regularly review their financial performance, identify trends, and adjust strategies accordingly. This ensures adaptability to changing market conditions and regulatory requirements.
- **Risk Management:** Implement robust risk management
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practices to address liquidity risk associated with varying Cash-Deposit Ratios. Stress testing and scenario analysis can help banks prepare for adverse situations and maintain financial stability.

- **Benchmarking:** Compare financial ratios and ROI with industry benchmarks and peers to gain insights into competitive positioning. Benchmarking can identify areas where improvements are needed to remain competitive and improve profitability.
- **Educate Stakeholders:** Banks should communicate their financial strategies and the role of key ratios to stakeholders, including investors, regulators, and employees. This transparency can build trust and align expectations.

In summary, the findings emphasize the importance of strategic financial management for small finance banks in India. By optimizing cash management, balancing credit exposure, refining investment strategies, diversifying revenue streams, and implementing robust risk management practices, these banks can enhance profitability while navigating the complexities of the banking landscape.

Conclusion:

ANOVA analysis highlights significant variations among different small finance banks in India regarding their financial ratios. The Cash-Deposit Ratio, Credit-Deposit Ratio, Ratio of Deposits to Total Liabilities, and Return on Investments show highly significant differences between bank groups, indicating distinct financial strategies and performance. The Investment-Deposit Ratio also differs significantly between groups, underscoring diversity in investment practices. This analysis underscores the importance of assessing and comparing these financial ratios to gain insights into the banks' operational and financial characteristics, guiding decision-making within the sector. It was found that higher Cash - Deposit Ratios and Credit - Deposit Ratios are associated with lower returns on investments. The negative coefficients indicate this negative relationship. Additionally, the Investment - Deposit Ratio and Ratio of Deposits to Total Liabilities also exhibit negative associations with returns. However, only the Cash - Deposit Ratio is statistically significant, emphasizing its substantial impact on returns. The other ratios do not significantly predict returns in this model. This underscores the significance of cash management strategies in influencing returns while suggesting that other factors may need further examination in the analysis.

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